

A LAVA FLOW SIMULATION EXPERIENCE ORIENTED TO DISASTER RISK REDUCTION, EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS AND RESPONSE DURING THE 2021 VOLCANIC ERUPTION IN CUMBRE VIEJA, LA PALMA.

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Abstract

Lava flows are one of the hazards involved in a volcanic eruption, and although they rarely cause the loss of human life, they are highly destructive in terms of damage to property and economic activity. Therefore, the management of volcanic disasters requires fast and accurate information on the behaviour and evolution of the flows, mainly related to their extension, displacement, and trajectory. This was the case during the disaster linked to the volcanic event that occurred on the island of La Palma in the Cumbre Vieja area at the end of 2021, which lasted eighty-five days. This paper describes part of the work performed by many different groups to provide predictive information aimed at feeding the early warning system set up during the disaster. This case shows the experience in the use of a probabilistic simulation algorithm implemented in the Q-LavHA plugin for the QGIS software, which is both easily accessible and applicable, to analyze its features in detail, as well as its predictive capacity. The results show that the model can efficiently and quickly satisfy the demand for this type of information, and its high similarity value is also validated by the Kappa index.

Keywords: Lava flow simulation; Volcanic hazards; Disaster risk reduction; Early warning; La Palma

1. INTRODUCTION

Lava flows are one of the main hazards during the course of effusive volcanic eruptions posing a risk to the population, and therefore require constant monitoring. In general, lava flows rarely cause loss of human life (Biganman *et al.*, 2013), since their low circulation speed usually allows a timely reaction and risk prevention and mitigation measures to be put in place (Carracedo *et al.*, 2001), such as the evacuation of people, transportable assets and belongings. That said, the effectiveness of these measures in the context of planning the response during a volcanic emergency can be more effective with improved knowledge and the ability to not only predict the behavior of the lava flow, but, above all, its likely path.

Knowledge of how lava flows move has been extensively studied by the interpretation of lava flow morphology (Hagiwara, 1941; Manakami, 1951; Shaw *et al.*, 1968, Pinkerton, 1978). These studies confirm the similarity of their behavior with a Bingham liquid where the flow characteristics are determined by a yield stress (Hulme, 1974). The yield stress depends in turn on the viscosity of the liquid, and this depends on factors such as temperature. The physical properties, the volume of lava emissions and local conditions

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42 such as topography, are also parameters that have been studied to gain a better
43 understanding of lava flow behavior.

44 In recent decades, not only have advances been made in the knowledge of lava flow
45 characteristics, but computer science and GIS have also been improved. Thanks to this
46 progress much of the research effort in this field has been directed towards the
47 development of dynamic simulation models. These models try to imitate the behaviour
48 of this phenomenon with the aim of improving both our knowledge and our ability to
49 predict it. In general, simulation experiences are based on numerical models applied to
50 geographic space, with a predominant use of cellular automata, and where the cell states
51 are usually binary (lava, non-lava), e.g. Felpeto *et al.* (2008) although examples of
52 prototypes that add states of solidified and fluid lava, in three-dimensional systems, were
53 found in the literature search (Harris and Rowland, 2001; Hidaka *et al.*, 2005). In addition,
54 there are deterministic and probabilistic approaches which specify a set of rules to drive
55 the cell state change, e.g. non-lava to lava. The first approach provides results on
56 discrete values and locations based on the interaction of several lava properties, such
57 as effusion rate, temperature, viscosity, rheological properties (density, viscosity, yield
58 stress), chemical composition, crystallinity, etc. and environmental properties, where the
59 topography is always included as a factor (Harris and Rowland, 2001; Hidaka *et al.*,
60 2005; Ishiara *et al.*, 1990; Young and Wadge, 1990; Bilotta *et al.*, 2012; Mossoux *et al.*,
61 2016); the second approach estimates the most probable path and the extension of the
62 flows by basically using environmental characteristics (relief: aspect and slope) where a
63 set of parameters need to be calibrated, such as lava thickness or constant values to
64 simulate the yield stress (Felpeto *et al.*, 2001; Favalli *et al.*, 2005; Damiani *et al.*, 2006).
65 These parameters can be empirically calibrated using a statistical method or by applying
66 a machine learning algorithm.

67 Generally speaking, the deterministic model approaches provide accurate simulation
68 results that can even predict the velocity, the shape and other dimensional and structural
69 characteristics of the lava flow other than the likely path of the lava flows. Nonetheless,
70 they usually require a set of data that is not always available in real time during the
71 eruptive process. Moreover, during such situations the operating response teams do not
72 need such accurate information about the lava flow evolution and its properties, but
73 having a map showing the geographic spaces that will be invaded by the lava could be
74 critical. From this perspective, probabilistic methods such as the LAVA FLOWS model
75 [8] or the DOWNFLOW model by Favalli *et al.* (2005) seem to be more effective in terms
76 of the speed required during the emergency. Furthermore, these algorithms are able to
77 run and produce predictions only with a suitable Digital Elevation Model.

78 In the case of the disaster caused by the strombolian-Hawaiian volcanic eruption in
79 Cumbre Vieja on the island La Palma in the last four months of 2021, industrial buildings,
80 infrastructures, crops, villages, and population were not only threatened by the lava flows
81 but also affected by the different volcanic hazards. In this respect, the lava destroyed
82 many of these assets, dramatically burying all that it found in its path. The civil protection
83 deployment coordinated by PEVOLCA (Volcanic Emergency Plan for the Canary
84 Islands) needed the best available information on the evolution of the volcano activity on
85 a daily basis to manage the situation. The successive vents of the eruptive fissure were
86 located about 900 meters above an area of dispersed residential land use, small villages
87 and a set of parallel and vital roads connecting some of the main economic activity nodes

88 of the island. The geomorphology of the land corresponds to that of a young geological
89 ramp of less than 20,000 years (Carracedo *et al.*, 2001) where the topography does not
90 always clearly show the slope and the drainage channels are still not well built (Romero,
91 1990). In this context, PEVOLCA and its human resources (formed by members of the
92 Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN), Instituto Volcanológico de Canarias (INVOLCAN),
93 Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME), Instituto Español de Oceanografía
94 (IEO), Universidad de La Laguna (ULL) and Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
95 (ULPGC)) requested continuous information about the evolution of the lava flows and
96 their likely occupation. Therefore, a probabilistic lava flow predictive model was used to
97 provide the necessary information for risk reduction and management. In order to do this,
98 the authors participated collaboratively, in collaboration with the Island Council
99 technicians, to provide data from the quasi real time flow simulations and to contribute
100 to the emergency management to reduce the risk of disaster. However, the authors were
101 not members of the PEVOLCA scientific team.

102 One of the main goals of the present work was to accurately estimate the parameters of
103 the LAVA FLOWS simulation model (Felpeto *et al.*, 2001) used in the Q-LavHA plugin
104 for QGIS software (Mossoux *et al.*, 2016) to simulate the lava flows of past volcanic
105 events in La Palma, and the application of the model in the recent eruption which
106 occurred in Cumbre Vieja, La Palma in 2021. The use of the algorithm during the 2021
107 volcanic emergency, the simulation process and the technical steps followed are
108 described below to show the effectiveness and usefulness of the model in terms of
109 accuracy, but to also demonstrate its value as an accessible and easy-to-use tool for
110 response management in eruptive events with characteristics similar to those in the
111 eruptive process on the island of La Palma in 2021.

112 **2. VOLCANIC DISASTER CONTEXT**

113 The island of La Palma is one of the seven islands belonging to the Canary archipelago
114 and is considered the most volcanically active island, given that seven of the fifteen
115 historical eruptive events that have taken place in the Canary Islands in the last 500
116 years, since the first records began, have occurred in La Palma (Troll and Carracedo,
117 2016). La Palma is an island with a triangular base, which can be differentiated into the
118 following two large topographical units: the Taburiente Volcano, in the north, and Cumbre
119 Vieja, in the south. The latter is where volcanic activity has been concentrated for
120 150,000 years (De la Nuez *et al.*, 2018). Cumbre Vieja is a volcanic ridge characterized
121 by monogenic eruptions which occupies an area of 220 km² and has a length of 20 km
122 arranged in a north-south direction (Figure 1a). Although emission centers can be found
123 distributed throughout its surface, with poorly defined fractures, there was a
124 reorganization of volcanism twenty thousand years ago and these fractures began to line
125 up in the center of the ridge, in the current NS axis (Day *et al.*, 1999). All the historical
126 eruptions that have taken place on the island are classified as being fissural in nature, in
127 other words, they have the appearance of several emission centers distributed along
128 eruptive alignments that function simultaneously or alternatively. In addition, all the flows
129 from these eruptions, with the exception of those from Montaña Quemada (ca. 1430-
130 1447), have reached the sea and increased the surface area of the island due to the
131 formation of lava deltas. It should be noted that the geologically young age of the area
132 means that there are few erosive forms. Even so, there are indications of an incipient

133 drainage network with simple channels, without defined headwaters, or even without the
134 channels being connected to the sea (Romero, 1990).

135 *Figure 1. Geographic setting of La Palma and 2021 eruption. a) Topographic units and historical*
136 *eruptions. b) 2021 Eruption, showing volcanic vents, lava flow paths and affected buildings and*
137 *roads*

138
139 In this context, on September 19, 2021, a new eruption began in the northwest sector of
140 Cumbre Vieja and lasted for eighty-five days, becoming the longest recorded historical
141 eruption on the island and breaking the trend that these were of increasingly shorter
142 duration (Troll and Carracedo, 2016). In line with the previous historical eruptions in the
143 Canary Islands, the volcanic event was characterized being of a strombolian fissural

144 eruptive typology with phreatomagmatic pulses, reaching Volcanic Explosivity Index
145 (VEI) of 3. In addition, the fissural nature of the eruption led to the opening of eleven
146 vents over the course of the eruptive process, some of which expelled lava
147 simultaneously, a fact that caused the overlapping of lava flows at times. As a result,
148 after the end of the eruption, six craters were aligned in a NW-SE direction along a 557m
149 fissure. On the other hand, according to the data provided by the PEVOLCA scientific
150 committee, the total amount of material emitted was more than 200Mm³, and the
151 estimated area occupied by the lava flows was 1,200ha. Similarly, the lava flows, which
152 are characterized by the majority presence of aa-type lavas, have a mean average
153 thickness of 12m that, on occasions, reached maximum heights of up to 70m. Besides,
154 with regard to the subaerial route of the lava, its longitudinal development is 6.5 km and
155 its cross section is 3.3 km at the most equidistant points. Furthermore, some of these
156 lava flows entered the sea, giving rise to an increase in the island's surface area of 48ha
157 by creating two platforms in the form of fans, known as lava deltas. These lava structures,
158 in turn, are supported by the materials from the emitting centers whose advance below
159 the water is up to 1.1km, occupying an area of more than 21ha (IGME, 2022).

160 **3. DATA SOURCE AND METHODS**

161 **3.1. Data source**

162 The present work uses sources of information on the geographic data necessary for the
163 simulation of lava flows. The data used is mainly divided into three groups: elevation
164 models, location of emission points and evolution of the flow perimeter. Two different
165 Digital Elevation Models (DEM) were used over the course of the eruptive process, both
166 with a resolution of 5 m. The first DEM used was prior to the start of the eruption and is
167 available in the open data of Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN), the institution in charge
168 of volcanic surveillance in Spain. A new DEM, including the changes in the previous
169 topography caused by the eruptive process, was built during the course of the eruption.
170 In addition, the perimeters of the lava flows shared on the open data website of the
171 Cabildo de La Palma (<https://www.opendatalapalma.es/>) (Cabildo de La Palma, 2022)
172 have been used to perform the validation of the simulations.

173 The location of the emission centers was initially obtained from the observations of the
174 local emergency teams deployed on the ground. Subsequently, the activation of the
175 remote imaging services provided by the Copernicus program allowed a more precise
176 location of the emission centers.

177 **3.2. Methods**

178 Given the objectives of the present work, the methodology described below is not only
179 aimed at describing the model used and the validity of the results, but also presents the
180 experience of lava flow simulations before and during the volcanic eruption in Cumbre
181 Vieja in La Palma. In this regard, (1) the choice of the model used, its operation and the
182 justification of its previous calibration results are described here (Martín-Raya, 2020); (2)
183 data were exchanged between the technicians belonging to the emergency groups and
184 the research group to perform the simulations; and (3) the method and results of the
185 validation of the simulations performed during the eruption are explained.

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3.2.1. Model selection, operation, previous calibration and validation

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188 Given the urgent need for information from PEVOLCA and considering the difficulties
 189 concerning the availability of all the parameters related to the characteristics of the lava
 190 (rheology, viscosity, temperature...) and to the eruption itself (such as the rate of
 191 emission or the flow rate), the use of deterministic models was ruled out and a
 192 probabilistic algorithm with low input data requirements was chosen instead. In this case,
 193 the LAVA FLOWS probabilistic model (Felpeto *et al.*, 2001 and 2007) was selected,
 194 which requires few minimum parameters and, therefore, is of great value and utility in
 195 emergency situations. This model simulates the probable trajectories that the lava flow
 196 fronts will take assuming that the topography plays the main role in the advance of the
 197 flow. In addition, this model is incorporated into the Q-LavHA software (Mossoux *et al.*, 2016), a QGIS plugin that is both easy to use and readily available.

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199 Felpeto's model (Felpeto *et al.*, 2001) expresses, from a digital elevation model (DEM),
 200 the probability that a cell is flooded by lava. An algorithm based on the Monte Carlo
 201 method is used for the calculation of probability. Starting from the emission center, the
 202 model assumes that the flow propagates from the central cell towards one of the eight
 203 cells surrounding it, calculating the flow probability (Figure 2), based on the altitude
 204 differences, by applying the following formula:

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$$P_i = \frac{\Delta h_i}{\sum_{j=1}^8 \Delta h_j} \quad i = 1,2,3, \dots, 8$$

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207 Where P_i is the flow probability, Δh_i is the difference in height between the central cell
 208 and each of the eight surrounding cells

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209 *Figure 2. Schema showing how the algorithm works. The central cell is the last one to be*
 210 *simulated. The surrounding cells are computed and the lava flow path evolves to the highest*
value of P_i cell.

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Source: Adapted from Moosux et al., 2016

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214 It should be remembered that if the difference (Δh_i) is negative, the probability will be 0,
 215 because the propagation of lava uphill is impossible. However, the model has corrective
 216 factors that allow the lava to flow over small obstacles or depressions, so the thickness
 217 (h_c) of the lava is always added to the value of each cell before calculating Δh_i .
 Furthermore, since lava can fill in pre-existing depressions and continue advancing, a

218 larger corrective factor (h_p) is introduced. This is applied if the cell is completely
 219 surrounded by others of a greater height, and even considering the height of the lava
 220 flow, the lava flow could not flow over them. Therefore, as can be seen in Figure 3, the
 221 simulation progresses smoothly until it encounters a depression that it is unable to move
 222 over. Therefore, the h_p correction is added and when it exceeds the next pixel elevation,
 223 the simulation continues.

224 *Figure 3. Schematic representation of how the correcting factors work. The lava evolves on the*
 225 *topography and when a depression is found H_p is applied to pass over it (Mossoux et al., 2016)*

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227 After determining which cells could be affected by the flow by calculating the probability
 228 for each one, a random cumulative probabilistic value (S_i) is calculated by applying the
 229 Monte Carlo method to select the cell which the flow will propagate across. Several paths
 230 are calculated where the flow cannot return backwards and the highest probabilities
 231 coincide with the areas with the greatest slopes. After each path, a probability of being
 232 affected is laid on each pixel (P_j). This probability is added with the rest to define the final
 233 pixel probability. The described model allows the configuration of the desired number of
 234 iterations when performing a simulation, although it should be considered that the
 235 recommended minimum to obtain good results is 1,500 (Mossoux et al., 2020). After this
 236 process, and following Monte Carlo method, a random number between zero and one is
 237 drawn by the algorithm and compared with S_i . If the random number falls within the
 238 interval $[S_i - 1, S_i]$, the pixel is selected as the next pixel on the lava flow path (Mossoux
 239 et al., 2016). The cell will be flooded by the lava flow if:

$$240 \quad S_i = \sum_{j=1}^i P_j \quad S_i - 1 \leq n_{rnd} < S_i$$

241 P_j : probability of being affected in each iteration using Monte Carlo.

242 n_{rnd} = random number between 0 and 1, calculated by the algorithm each time.

243 If the result is negative, this means that the lava has entered a depression that even
 244 when applying the corrective factors, it is not able to flow over it and, therefore, the model
 245 stops.

246 Knowing the final location of the lava flow and determining at what point it will stop is not
 247 a straightforward process, since it depends on complex factors, which are difficult to
 248 obtain and vary among eruptions (Daminani et al., 2006). However, the Euclidean
 249 maximum length (L_{max}) option incorporated in the model itself was used to prepare a
 250 quick and useful forecast for the emergency situation. This value can be easily estimated

251 by studying, for example, the lengths of historical lava flows. When the lava flow reaches
252 the set distance, the model ends. For this reason, and given the characteristics of this
253 specific case, the simulations performed here are parameterized to force the lava flows
254 to reach the sea, given that the main demand for information involves the trajectory of
255 the fronts and their foreseeable occupation.

256 *Figure 4. Simulation validation results using data from the eruption of the San Juan Volcano*
257 *(1949)*

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Basemap Source: Instituto Geográfico Nacional (National Geographic Institute)

260 Q-LavHA has an algorithm that, by means of a fitness index, allows the simulation of the
261 lava flows to be validated by comparing them with a real lava flow, similar in origin,
262 composition and morphology. Therefore, a previous step to performing the simulations
263 was the calibration of the parameters used to achieve a good goodness of fit through an
264 empirical trial-error method (Table 1). Here, the lava flow from the eruption of the San
265 Juan Volcano in La Palma (1949) was used to perform the calibration (Figure 4). The
266 optimal way to carry out this calibration would be to use the pre-eruptive topography as
267 is usually done (e.g. Rodríguez et al., 2019; Becerril et al., 2021). However, the first
268 available topographies of the island of La Palma date from the late 1960s and there are
269 no previous elevation models. As such, there is also no information on the thickness of
270 the flows, which is needed to accurately eliminate the lava body. For both of these
271 reasons, the DEM for the year 2021 was used here.

272 In addition, data on the historical eruptions in the Canary Islands were considered, such
273 as the thickness of the lava flow (Carracedo *et al.*, 2004) and the maximum length of the
274 lava flows in eruptions in La Palma. Regarding the latter, the greatest length reached by
275 a lava flow in the volcanic eruptive events in La Palma is ten kilometres in the case of
276 the Montaña Quemada eruption (ca. 1430–1447). However, although most of the flows
277 have maximum visible lengths notably shorter than those of Montaña Quemada, with
278 paths that do not exceed eight kilometers, this distance (10 km) was considered

279 appropriate to ensure that the model simulated lava flows which are able to reach the
280 coast, as happened in six of the seven historical eruptions on La Palma (Romero, 1990).

281 Table 1. Parameter values obtained by the calibration process and used in the simulations

Parameter	Meaning	Value
h_c	Lava flow thickness	3 m
h_p	Correction factor	2 m
L_{max}	Maximum length achievable by the lava flows	10 km
Threshold	The minimum probability considered on simulation results	0.03%
Iterations	Number of Montecarlo packs	10,000

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283 The fitness index compares the overlapping (true positive) between the real flow and the
284 simulation. After conducting numerous tests, the highest fitness index value obtained
285 was 0.3 (Figure 4), that is, 30% of the simulation adjust to the real flow. It should be said
286 that this value would improve if the pre-eruptive topography were used. Although
287 Mossoux et al. (2016) suggest 0.5 as the optimal value, 0.3 is considered sufficient due
288 to the objective of the calibration. Furthermore, false positives and negatives are also an
289 important consideration to validate the calibration of the parameters, so these values
290 must be taken into account to correctly interpret the results. For effective use in risk
291 management, overestimating (false positive) implies applying an acceptable precaution
292 in the context of hazard assessment, while underestimating (false negative) the affected
293 area would be problematic (Mossoux *et al.*, 2016). In this regard, although 70% of the
294 surface is overestimated (0.7 false positive), only 5% is underestimated (0.05 false
295 negative), which means it is useful in an emergency.

296 **3.2.2. Development of simulations during the volcanic emergency**

297 The objective of the lava flow simulations in the present work is to provide information
298 for the emergency management teams about the possible trajectory of the flows,
299 especially during their progress on the ground. As explained above, the geographic
300 location of the volcanic event corresponds to an initial location of an eruptive fissure at
301 high levels on the island (900 m) in a location with a small population and little human
302 activity, but from which lava flows run towards the coast (elevation 0). In this context,
303 emergency managers and citizens require information quickly about the possible
304 trajectory of the emerging and advancing lava flows that are destroying buildings,
305 residential neighbourhoods, crops, and other infrastructure at lower levels which ends
306 up buried under the path of the lava as it moves towards the sea. However, the direction
307 of the lava flows cannot be easily predicted because the channel networks are not clearly
308 defined due to the geologically young age of the area and its little erosion.

309 As the volcanic episode unfolded, the data and the flow of information generally
310 improved, as a result of the work of the PEVOLCA scientific committee teams and the
311 observation of local emergency operations, as well as national detachments specialized
312 in the response to disaster situations, such as the Military Emergency Unit (UME, in
313 Spanish), in addition to remote observation mainly provided by the European emergency
314 and early warning service Copernicus. There were constant changes in the behaviour,
315 evolution, extension, and displacement of the flows, as well as the emission points and
316 the morphology of the vents. Therefore, the data and information generated were also

317 highly dynamic. Furthermore, and along the same lines, the demand for predictive
318 information on the progress of the lava flows became a critical factor in monitoring the
319 entire volcanic process.

320 In short, the entire eruptive episode and the changes in the evolution of the flows, the
321 migration of the eruptive vents and the changes in the topography themselves, varied as
322 much as the availability of data and information does. In addition, the simulations carried
323 out can be classified according to the evolutionary circumstances of this specific eruptive
324 event and the availability of data during it, and as such the following simulations are
325 described below:

326 **Simulation 1.** This was performed at the beginning of the volcanic episode between
327 September 19th and 31st 2021, when the cone had not yet been defined and, although
328 there were three main vents, up to nine emission points were counted along the fissure.
329 The lava flows were aa type, highly viscous, with mean average speeds of 200 meters
330 per hour, decreasing to less than 1 m/h in some stages, especially in the furthest points
331 from the eruptive vents (IGME, 2022), and notable thicknesses were observed in the
332 direct observation of lava flows that, in some of the more depressed areas, exceeded
333 fifteen meters. The first simulation was performed on September 20th, using both the
334 imprecise location of the aforementioned three main vents and the parameters of the
335 previous calibration (Figure 3) as well as the DEM available in the abovementioned open
336 data of the IGN.

337 The algorithm in Q-LavHA allows the configuration of the model to simulate lava flow
338 emission either from all three vents at the same time, from a series of points evenly
339 arranged along a fissure or from each vent individually. The last option was chosen,
340 subsequently adding the probabilities of being flooded in each simulation. Thus, the
341 areas that were in danger of being occupied by the lava flow were identified and the
342 probabilities of such an event were obtained. To better understand the existing danger
343 in each area, the resulting probabilities were defined using the quantil method as this
344 has been used in other cases with other hazards (Tehrany *et al.*, 2014; Jaari *et al.*, 2014;
345 Rahmati *et al.*, 2016) (Figure 6), and with extremely low values being discarded (Table
346 2).

347 Table 2. Standardization of probability values.

Probability	Standard value	Category
<0.0003	0	Discarded
0.0003-0.0007	1	Very Low
0.0007-0.001	2	Low
0.001-0.005	3	Moderate
0.005-0.01	4	High
>0.01	5	Very High

348 **Simulation 2.** This simulation corresponds to the intermediate stage of the event
349 between October 1st and 20th. During this period, the previous lava flows, as well as the
350 fall of pyroclasts and ash, modified the topography of the affected areas. At the same
351 time, the outer layers of the flows cooled down and the formation of volcanic tubes and
352 lava channels between levees occurred. As a result, the lava flows, which were generally

353 more fluid than in the initial stage, mainly circulated on top of the lava flows emplaced in
354 the first stage of the eruption. However, the appearance of a new emission point, to the
355 north, needed new simulations to predict the paths of the lava flows that threatened to
356 cover new land. On the other hand, the main front of the initial lava flows had already
357 reached the sea, but new lava flow fronts, generated by processes of new lava flowing
358 over existing lava, threatened new areas which had not yet been affected.

359 The location of the new eruptive vent located further north and the perimeter occupied
360 by the lava flows were required to perform this simulation. In addition, it was necessary
361 to obtain information on the new topography generated by the materials ejected by the
362 volcano, mainly the lava flows. Given the rush and lack of new terrain elevation data, a
363 decision was taken to perform a simulated mean average elevation of the terrain
364 occupied by the previous flows using a calculation based on observation and data taken
365 in the field work. In this respect, a mean average extrusion of seven meters was made
366 to all the cells occupied by the polygon representing the extension of the flows at the
367 time. This extrusion contributes, above all, to modelling the effect of the levees and fronts
368 of the previous flows in a more realistic way. These morphologies form important
369 obstacles to be overcome by the active flows running adjacent to or with transversal
370 paths to the previously partially or totally cooled flows.

371 **Simulation 3.** This simulation concerns the last stage which was specifically studied for
372 this eruption and, above all, in the context of the present work, covering the period from
373 October 20th to December 14th, 2021. As observed throughout the first month of
374 eruption, the flow thickness was greater than the simulated thickness. As a result, it was
375 decided to change the simulation parameters to be consistent with the real situation, by
376 adjusting the values of H_c and H_p to 7 and 4 meters, respectively. The lava flows generally
377 continued to move, for the most part, either on top of the previous lava flows, or through
378 volcanic tubes. Several lava channels were seen running to the sea without occupying
379 new land. However, some fronts, even with unoccupied space ahead, advanced slowly.
380 Lateral thickening of lava flows was also produced by new lava flowing over existing lava.
381 These overflows sometimes formed lava streams that flowed alongside the larger lava
382 flows, forming small fronts similar to those directly produced by an emission point. This
383 situation occurred, at this stage, especially in the south since the flows from the north
384 flowed mostly over the pre-existing flows. This is where a new vent appeared in the
385 altitudinal strip of the initial fissure and it was therefore necessary to perform a new
386 simulation. This vent to the south, which initially only expelled gases, ash and some
387 pyroclasts, began to extrude lava around October 25th, affecting new areas in the
388 southernmost part, burying part of a cemetery at around 550 m above sea level. Below
389 this altitudinal strip, the advance of the lava flow to the south was mainly produced by
390 the abovementioned overflows (Figure 5). Although consideration was given to simulate
391 these overflows which were taking place at lower levels, it was decided to use the
392 modelled flow for the southern vent as a reference. To a large degree, this simulation
393 also covered the terrain that could be occupied by lava from the aforementioned frontal
394 and lateral overflows at lower levels.

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Figure 5. Schema of the overflow processes where spills can be seen at lower altitudinal levels in last stages.

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3.2.3. Validation method

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Since the main objective of these simulations is focused on predicting the trajectory and occupation of the flows, the index proposed by Cohen (1960) called the Kappa Index was used to perform the validation of the simulations. This is a measure that expresses the coherence existing between objects observed in a two-dimensional plane, in this case, between the lava flow simulations and the actual lava flows of the eruption. Its computation focuses on the proportion of agreement between the two compared objects, taking into account the overestimates and underestimates of p_c , in this case between two cell states (lava or non-lava), and is calculated as follows (Walker, 2010).

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$$K = \frac{p_0 - p_c}{1 - p_c}$$

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Where p_c corresponds to the expected corrected proportion and p_0 is the observed corrected proportion. These parameters are calculated as follows:

410

$$p_0 = \frac{TP+TN}{N}$$

$$p_c = \frac{(TP + FN)(TP + FP) + (FP + TN)(FN + TN)}{N^2}$$

411

412

413

414

where TP is true positive from the simulated lava flow, TN: true negative, FP: false positive, FN: false negative and N is the number of pixels in the map (Figure 6) (Sahani and Gosh, 2021). The results of the calculation are between 0 and 1, where 1 corresponds to perfect consistency.

415
416

Figure 6. Schema of Kappa index. It compares simulated and real lava flow occupation and estimates the similarity between each of them.

417

418 The Kappa index analyses and compares the cells of each of the layers, establishing
419 where the agreements and discrepancies are found (Figure 5). To correctly apply the
420 Kappa index in a geographic information system, it is necessary to standardize the
421 information to be used. Therefore, the information must be in raster format, have the
422 same extension and be classified in values 1 and 0 (where 1 is lava and 0 is non-lava).
423 It should be noted that, in this case, to make the comparison between the real flows and
424 the simulations, the decision was taken to eliminate the new lava deltas formed offshore,
425 since the DEMs used in the model do not contain bathymetry data.

426 In the first moments of the eruption, the simulations occupied spaces that the real lava
427 flow did not, and which were later filled with the advance of the lava. Therefore, in order
428 to determine whether the simulation was accurate or not by using the Kappa index, it is
429 necessary to wait for the end of the eruption when the lava has already occupied the
430 whole territory. However, it was decided to subject the simulations to a successive
431 comparison of the simulation results with the area occupied by the lava flows at
432 successive times of between five and ten days, depending on the observed rate of
433 volcanic activity. This makes it possible to observe how the Kappa index approaches 1
434 (greater degree of similarity) as the perimeter of the land occupied by new flows
435 increases or, in other words, to check the validity of the simulations over time.

436 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

437 The results presented below are mainly aimed at describing the simulation process and
438 the technical steps followed, as well as the capacity of the model to predict the path of
439 the lava flows using a validation procedure based on the Kappa index.

440 As described in the methodological section above, based on a series of significant
441 changes in the evolution of the lava flows within the temporal evolution of the eruptive
442 phenomenon, three simulations were required at different times during the event. The
443 cartographic results are shown in Figure 7 (see dynamic version for figure 6)

444 The simulations were performed assuming that the volume of lava emitted was high
445 enough for the lava front to reach the coast, and as such the simulations are considered
446 valid when the Kappa index tends to reach the value 1 (maximum similarity) (Figure 7).

447 Figure 7. Results of lava flow simulations run during the volcanic eruption. The first two runs
448 were performed using the DEM available before the eruption and the last one with the new
449 updated DEM.

Simulation 1 Pre-eruptive DEM Lava flow perimeter: 30 september 2021

Simulation 2 Pre-eruptive DEM Lava flow perimeter: 14 october 2021

Simulation 3 Updated DEM Lava flow perimeter: 14 december 2021

450

451

Source: IGN (DEM 1); Island Council (DEM 2,3; lava perimeters; fabric)

452
453
454

Figure 8. Evolution of the lava flow during the eruption, comparison with the simulations and the results of the Kappa index. The number of days of eruption and the date are shown, as well as the simulation performed using the Kappa index in each case.

455
456

Source: IGN (basemap)

457 During the first half of the eruption, where the lava repeatedly occupied new ground, the
458 index grew rapidly, from 0.212 to 0.731, on October 30th (Figure 8, day 41). After this, a
459 slower increase of the index was observed until it reached the maximum of 0.793. This
460 slowdown coincides with the stagnation of the affected surface, whose evolution is
461 similar. During the first forty-one days of the process, 965 ha were occupied, almost 80%
462 of the total, as shown in Figure 9, while in the second half of the eruption process only
463 255 more ha were invaded (the remaining 20%). This is because the lava began to flow
464 more fluidly over already covered land or through volcanic tubes.

465 The noteworthy falls in the goodness of fit produced by the Kappa index mainly occurred
 466 in the intermediate stage of the eruptive process and there was also a less pronounced
 467 one in the final stage (Figure 9). The falls in the Kappa index were produced by the
 468 addition of a new simulated lava flow and, in both cases, this was followed by an
 469 increase in the Kappa index because the lava flows covered the predicted area, which
 470 reinforces and strengthens the accuracy of the model. On the other hand, the slight
 471 decrease that occurred at the end of the process is related to the overflows that occurred
 472 around the cone as a result of an intensification of the eruption due to the final degassing
 473 process. This becomes clear by observing the evolution of occupied hectares, where a
 474 more pronounced increase in the trend was observed in the final two days of the eruptive
 475 process, occupying 4% of the total area affected, that is, 41ha. This explains why,
 476 although an index value of 0.8 was reached on December 12th, the final result is slightly
 477 lower (0.793).

478 Figure 9. Temporal evolution of the Kappa index (principal axis) and hectares of land covered
 479 by lava (secondary axis) during the eruption

480

481

Source: Island Council (lava surface)

482 It should be noted that two discordant zones stand out at the end of the eruptive process:
 483 one spatially overestimating and the other underestimating the area. The first
 484 corresponds to the southern strip (simulation 3 in Figure 7), where the short duration of
 485 the eruption left the areas of moderate and low susceptibility unoccupied, as mentioned
 486 above. On the other hand, around the cone, a marked discordance can be seen, due to
 487 the continuous changes in its morphology, related to the process of construction and
 488 reconfiguration. However, according to the classifications for interpreting values derived
 489 from the Kappa index prepared by Landis and Koch (1977), Fleiss (1971) or Cicchetti
 490 (1984), the results obtained are relevant and adjust with a high level of accuracy to the
 491 reality observed during the entire eruptive event. In addition, the success and usefulness
 492 of the simulations require knowing the precise location of the emission points as soon as
 493 possible (Capello *et al.*, 2016) to favour effective response processes. However,
 494 providing accuracy rapidly is a complex matter as this emergency has shown. The

495 maximum accuracy of the location of the vents can be dispensed with to a certain extent,
496 especially at the beginning of the episode bearing in mind the complexity of fissural
497 eruptions in terms of the location of emission points.

498 Ultimately, this work not only validates and complements, but also shows the high
499 applicability of the previous studies of Felpeto (2001, 2007). In the sense that lava flows
500 are complex systems whose behavior and evolution are driven by the interaction of many
501 factors such as temperature, degree of crystallization, rheology and the environment
502 (Bilotta *et al.*, 2012). Many of the models that simulate the spatial and dynamic behaviour
503 of a natural or human phenomenon using cellular automata are based on the complexity
504 theory (Díaz Pacheco, 2015). This means that, among other things, these models are
505 able to find patterns in apparent chaos and imitate the interactions between factors and
506 elements (temperature, topography, chemical composition...), reproducing, in this case,
507 the behavior of the lava flows using a set of simple rules (Tobler, 1979; Couclelis, 1985;
508 White and Engelen, 1993). When information from past eruptions exist, it is possible to
509 compile data about those parameters and use them to simulate lava flows (Harris *et al.*,
510 2011; Zuccarello *et al.*, 2022) or alternatively real-time measurements of time-averaged
511 discharge rates derived from satellite thermal infrared images can be used (e.g. Vicari *et al.*,
512 2011; Kaneko *et al.*, 2021) or even data from other eruptions in similar volcanic
513 contexts can be used. These deterministic models usually produce a more accurate
514 prediction of the likely paths and extension of lava flows, especially when the vents are
515 located far from the coastline and the final length of the flow is uncertain. However, in a
516 complex and sudden emergency situation, as was the case in La Palma, it is necessary
517 to know as quickly as possible which areas would be affected. Therefore, a probabilistic
518 model, despite being less accurate, is shown here to be the better option where previous
519 data did not exist and real-time data are poor, particularly at the beginning of the eruption.
520 One of the main advantages of the method used in the present work is its ability to
521 simulate a complex natural event and/or a non-linear phenomenon using a set of simple
522 rules integrated into one simple equation.

523 Many of the scientific works on lava flow simulation have traditionally been focused on
524 the characterization of the physical phenomenon (Sobradelo *et al.*, 2011; Barker *et al.*,
525 2015; Branca and Del Carlo, 2005; Cronin *et al.*, 2003; Umakoshi *et al.*, 2001) but there
526 are few works focused on the value of lava flow simulation as a risk management tool
527 (e.g. Favalli *et al.*, 2009; Favalli *et al.*, 2012; Becerril *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, the results
528 obtained here show the great value of the method designed here as an early warning
529 system for monitoring and forecasting a threat such as lava flows. In addition, elements
530 such as the predictive cartography developed during the eruptive process in La Palma
531 as a result of the continuous simulations helped to specify the decision-making
532 associated with a danger such as lava flows. The latter is in line with that expressed in
533 international reports such as the Global Assessment Report (2019), which emphasizes
534 the importance of taking actions to improve the monitoring, analysis and forecasting of
535 threats and their possible consequences. This, among other things, has made it possible
536 to enhance emergency management processes and guarantee correct decision-making
537 in highly relevant aspects such as preventive evacuation and multiple logistics tasks
538 related to emergencies (Marrero *et al.*, 2019).

539 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

540 The first steps of the present work were based on the calibration of the necessary
541 parameters to use the LAVA FLOWS algorithm (Felpeto, 2001) during the development
542 of the Tajogaite volcanic episode in 2021 on the island of La Palma. In order to do this,
543 data from historical eruptions that occurred on the island since 1400 were used,
544 especially those concerning the San Juan eruption in 1949, since part of its lava flow is
545 close to the 2021 eruption, showing similar lava flow behavior. This previous calibration
546 allowed our research group to use the algorithms to periodically supply early warning
547 information to the operative emergency team deployed in La Palma. The authors of the
548 present work did not have any role in the PEVOLCA (the regional emergency plan for
549 volcanic risk) scientific committee, but they voluntarily supplied this kind of information,
550 which was requested by the island government emergency operation team. In this
551 regard, this work attempts to show the results of a collaborative experience during a
552 volcanic emergency, between academics and the local administration. Everything
553 functioned as a coordinated and complementary support to the official work of
554 PEVOLCA.

555 The algorithms used are incorporated in the Q-LavHA plugin (Mossoux *et al.*, 2016),
556 which is easy to install and use in the free software QGIS, which makes it an accessible
557 tool, quick to use and readily applicable during an eruptive process requiring rapid and
558 precise predictive information about the evolution of the flows, especially in terms of their
559 possible trajectories and their occupation. In fact, this work also evaluates the capacity
560 of such algorithms implemented in applications of easy availability to be used in response
561 situations to a disaster of volcanic origin.

562 The results show that the model used here is of great value in meeting the demand for
563 information required by emergency operations. Its versatility, efficiency and low input
564 data requirement provide good simulation results during the risk management tasks to
565 mitigate the dangers inherent during a volcanic event and it does this in practically real
566 time. At least, and the present work demonstrates this, for the type of volcanic events
567 with characteristics similar to the one that occurred in La Palma in 2021.

568 The following three points should be mentioned, which could easily be improved for
569 future experiences. The first is that the accuracy of the calibration fitness index could be
570 improved by subtracting the topography generated by the lava flows of historical
571 eruptions used for calibration; secondly, it is crucial to have a more accurate location of
572 the active vents to improve the lava flow prediction; and thirdly, it is important to mention
573 that, after obtaining a low fitness index and a reasonable location of the vents, the results
574 of the simulations during the emergency showed a high degree of accuracy. This latter
575 point may be due to the regular topography of the area where there are ravines or
576 canyons which are not particularly abrupt.

577 Reducing the impact of a disaster requires anticipation and the present work also
578 highlights the importance of having systems in place capable of generating accurate
579 information during the occurrence of a volcanic event, especially at the beginning of the
580 eruption. Information about the location and the evolution of the eruptive vents is critical
581 to simulate lava flows and to use this type of probabilistic model based on cellular
582 automata. An accurate DEM (5x5 m is good enough), and a system which is able to
583 update this model in real time are also indispensable elements for lava flow simulation.

584 In addition, as this experience also shows, in order to successfully channel this type of
585 task, aimed at improving early warning systems, it is important to maintain constant
586 feedback between the observation teams deployed in the field and the agents and
587 scientists who perform the simulations.

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772 **Competing Interests**

773 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

774 **ETHICS DECLARATIONS**

775 **Conflict of interest**

776 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.